

Temporal Meta-Curiosity via Recurrent Self-Reinforcing Intrinsic Meta-Learning

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Abstract

Intrinsic curiosity has proven effective in reinforcement learning (RL), particularly in sparse-reward environments, by promoting exploration in the absence of explicit incentives. In parallel, meta-learning has emerged as a powerful tool for improving generalisation by enabling agents to learn how to learn. This paper explores the intersection of these two paradigms, proposing a framework in which agents develop temporal meta-curiosity, the capacity to learn what to be curious about over time. It is demonstrated that integrating intrinsic-only reward mechanisms with meta-learning architectures yields emergent, goal-directed behaviour, even in the complete absence of extrinsic rewards. The results highlight the feasibility and promise of self-reinforcing intrinsic meta-learning as a step toward more autonomous, self-structuring agents.

Keywords

reinforcement learning, intrinsic motivation, meta-learning, curiosity-driven agents, autonomous exploration, sparse environments, emergent behaviour

1. Introduction

Reinforcement learning (RL) is a machine learning paradigm in which intelligent agents interact with an environment to learn policies that maximise extrinsic rewards provided by that environment [1]. However, in many real-world settings, such rewards are sparse or entirely absent, limiting the applicability of reward-driven learning frameworks [2]. One increasingly promising solution is intrinsic curiosity, a mechanism that generates internal reward signals by incentivising the agent to explore unknown states, a process that mirrors certain biological drives.

In biological organisms, curiosity arises as a discomforting tension due to an information gap, and is shown to be tightly linked to exploratory behaviour driven by novelty and uncertainty [3]. However, not all novelty triggers curiosity, as recent work suggests that curiosity is selective and depends on factors such as confidence, importance, and perceived attainability of knowledge [4]. Moreover, curiosity is fundamentally temporal as it is shaped by when information is encountered and how urgently it is desired [5]. These findings imply that rational agents possess a meta-cognitive awareness of curiosity itself, not just being curious, but knowing what to be curious about and when.

In current RL frameworks, this deeper understanding is missing. Curiosity is typically framed as a static, task-oriented exploration signal [2], with little regard for temporal dynamics or meta-level adaptation. Agents are encouraged via intrinsic signals to explore for the sake of obtaining and maximising rewards, which, with some notable exceptions [6], all but ensures their continued ignorance of how to guide their own curiosity over time. As a result, intrinsic motivation remains shallow, treated as a fixed bonus rather than a learnable cognitive process. This static treatment assumes that curiosity is uniform across all states and time steps, neglecting the possibility that curiosity itself may evolve.

Such limitations constrain agents to reactive behaviour rather than reflective behaviour, preventing the formation of deeper exploratory strategies. Bridging this gap requires a learning system capable of conditioning its own curiosity over time, one that builds a history of how novelty leads to value, and generalises that knowledge across episodes. To address such shortcomings, in this work, a proof-of-concept meta-curiosity architecture, Recurrent Intrinsic Meta-Learner (RIML), is introduced. It

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is a recurrent, intrinsically motivated system capable of learning not just through curiosity, but by conditioning its own curiosity over time.

2. Methodology

RIML is a multi-step RL, sequential architecture comprised of spatiotemporal feature encoding, meta-episode acquisition and meta-policy training, and intrinsic reward-driven policy gradient.

Figure 1: The RIML architecture. The upper box shows the RL² inner loop, where the agent obtains episodic returns. The lower box depicts the outer loop, where the returns are used to refine the meta-policy.

2.1. Encoder

The encoder is a hybrid neural network designed to transform raw environment observations into compact spatiotemporal feature representations. It consists of a convolutional neural network (CNN) for spatial feature extraction and a gated recurrent unit (GRU) for temporal sequence modelling. CNNs are well-suited for processing image-based inputs due to their ability to learn hierarchical spatial features [7]. The GRU module captures temporal dependencies across frames, enabling the agent to condition actions on observation history. GRUs have been shown to offer performance comparable to long short-term memory (LSTM) units, while maintaining a simpler architecture and lower computational overhead [8]. The resulting feature vector is used as input for both the actor and intrinsic reward modules.

Formally, the CNN-GRU encoder transforms raw input observations x through successive convolutional layers with leaky rectified linear unit (leaky ReLU) activations. The CNN stack is defined as

$$f_{\text{cnn}}(x) = \sigma_{\text{leaky ReLU}}(\text{Conv}_n(\dots \text{Conv}_1(x))), \quad (1)$$

where each convolutional layer computes

$$\text{Conv}(x)^{(j)} = b^{(j)} + \sum_{k=1}^{C_{\text{in}}} W^{(j,k)} \star x^{(k)}. \quad (2)$$

Figure 2: The CNN-GRU encoder. Environment frames are processed by convolutional layers to extract spatial features, which are then passed to a GRU to model temporal dependencies.

The leaky ReLU activation is defined element-wise as

$$\sigma_{\text{leaky ReLU}}(z) = \begin{cases} z & \text{if } z > 0 \\ \alpha z & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where α corresponds to a small constant value. The resulting spatial feature tensor is then passed to the GRU for temporal integration. Let x_t be the flattened CNN feature vector at time t , and h_{t-1} the previous GRU hidden state. Then the GRU computes

$$r_t = \sigma(W_{ir}x_t + b_{ir} + W_{hr}h_{t-1} + b_{hr}) \quad (4)$$

$$z_t = \sigma(W_{iz}x_t + b_{iz} + W_{hz}h_{t-1} + b_{hz}) \quad (5)$$

$$n_t = \tanh(W_{in}x_t + b_{in} + r_t \odot (W_{hn}h_{t-1} + b_{hn})) \quad (6)$$

$$h_t = (1 - z_t) \odot n_t + z_t \odot h_{t-1}, \quad (7)$$

where W is the weight matrix, b is the bias, r_t is the reset gate, z_t is the update gate, n_t is the new gate, and h_t is the hidden state, which serves as the input representation for both the actor and intrinsic reward modules, conditioning them on the agent's observed temporal context.

2.2. Intrinsic Module

The intrinsic module is implemented using random network distillation (RND), a computationally efficient method for producing intrinsic rewards based on prediction error [9]. It consists of a fixed, randomly initialised target network and a trainable predictor network. The agent receives higher intrinsic reward when the predictor fails to approximate the target's output for a given observation, thereby encouraging exploration of novel or poorly understood states.

Figure 3: RND architecture. The feature vector x_t is passed through both a fixed target network f_{target} and a trainable predictor f_{pred} , producing outputs y_t and \hat{y}_t , respectively. The intrinsic reward r_t is computed as the squared prediction error.

2.3. Meta-Policy Training

Meta-policy training is performed using RL^2 , a meta-reinforcement learning approach in which an agent, parametrised by a recurrent neural network (RNN), learns to adapt its behaviour over time through interaction with sequences of episodes [10]. Instead of learning a policy directly, the agent learns an update rule embedded in its recurrent structure, allowing it to generalise across tasks and condition future behaviour on past experience.

The agent’s environment is modelled as a Markov Decision Process (MDP), defined by the tuple

$$\mathcal{M} = (\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{P}, r, p_0),$$

where \mathcal{S} is the set of states, \mathcal{A} the set of actions, $\mathcal{P} : \mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \Delta(\mathcal{S})$ the transition probability function, $r : \mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ the reward function, and $p_0 : \mathcal{S} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ the initial state distribution. The agent interacts with this MDP to learn a policy $\pi : \mathcal{S} \rightarrow \Delta(\mathcal{A})$ that maximises expected return. In practice, each meta-episode sampled from the environment produces a tuple

$$M = (\mathbf{s}_{1:T}, \mathbf{a}_{1:T}, \mathbf{r}_{1:T}),$$

where $\mathbf{s}_{1:T} \in \mathcal{S}^T$ is the sequence of observed states, $\mathbf{a}_{1:T} \in \mathcal{A}^T$ are actions sampled from the agent’s policy, and $\mathbf{r}_{1:T} \in \mathbb{R}^T$ are intrinsic rewards computed via RND. These tuples are collected and stored as meta-episodes for use in outer-loop policy updates. Note that both the environment’s transition dynamics \mathcal{P} and the initial state distribution p_0 are sampled implicitly and not explicitly modelled.

3. Experiment Setup

Hardware All experiments were run locally on a standard consumer laptop (Intel i7-13620H, 16 GB RAM, RTX 4050 Max-Q) without access to dedicated servers or cloud resources. Despite the compute limitations, the system was able to successfully demonstrate meta-curiosity, underscoring the architectural efficiency and conceptual design of RIML.

Environment The agent was trained on MiniGrid’s Empty-5x5-v0, Empty-8x8-v0, and Unlock-v0 environments using the Gymnasium framework. Each meta-episode consisted of multiple rollout segments, each with a maximum length of $N = 64$ steps, across $T = 5$ episodes.

Model Architecture The encoder consists of three convolutional layers followed by a GRU with 256 to 512 hidden units. The actor head is a two-layer multilayer perceptron (MLP) outputting logits for a categorical policy. The RND module comprises a randomly initialised target network (1 linear layer plus Tanh activation function) and a trainable predictor network (3 linear layers, layer normalisation, and leaky ReLU).

Intrinsic Reward and Normalisation Intrinsic reward was computed via the L2 error between the RND predictor and target outputs. Rewards were normalised online using a running mean and standard deviation filter. No extrinsic rewards were used for policy optimisation.

Training Procedure The model was trained using a modified REINFORCE-style objective. After every T meta-episodes, a batch of $K = 4$ episodes was sampled for a policy update, and $K = 2$ episodes were used per update. Gradient clipping was applied with a maximum norm of 0.5. The Adam optimiser was used with a learning rate of $1e-4$ and a cosine annealing learning rate scheduler.

Training Duration Training was run for 30 iterations, each consisting of meta-episode generation followed by a single policy update. Each full training cycle (30 iterations) took approximately 40 minutes on average, depending on episode length and CUDA memory constraints.

4. Results

Although RIML was trained using intrinsic rewards alone, extrinsic rewards began to emerge throughout training, indicating that the agent was capable of discovering and exploiting environment structure without any external incentive shaping. These extrinsic rewards remained sparse and oscillatory, reflecting the non-greedy nature of the learned policy.

Intrinsic rewards, as expected, declined steadily over time, suggesting a reduction in novelty as the agent became increasingly familiar with its surroundings. In parallel, RND loss stabilised, implying that the agent successfully internalised a novelty model. Interestingly, entropy did not decrease as is typical in converging policies and, instead, it remained high or increased, suggesting persistent uncertainty and deliberate exploratory behaviour. Taken together, these trends indicate that RIML does not converge toward deterministic exploitation. Rather, it maintains adaptive uncertainty and develops a temporally conditioned sense of what is worth exploring, and when.

Notably, RIML agents were not uniform. While the most common training outcome was an average agent that managed to generate modest extrinsic rewards, a far more interesting and emergent agent arose under uncertain conditions, its presence initially testified by training logs showing extrinsic rewards far in excess of intrinsic ones, high entropy, and stabilised RND loss.

Figure 4: Training metrics for the emergent agent on MiniGrid’s UnLock-v0 environment, visualised via TensorBoard. The plots reflect key dynamics underlying RIML’s meta-curiosity, such as the emergence of high extrinsic rewards despite intrinsic-only training, a steady decay in novelty, stabilised RND loss, and rising entropy, together suggesting a self-conditioned exploration strategy that resists policy collapse.

Characterised by a “monk-like” wandering and seeking behaviour, this agent exhibited unique emergent behaviours across multiple rollouts in various environments, notably UnLock-v0, where the following was observed:

- The agent frequently approached the locked door, appeared to hesitate, and turned away, even when it already possessed the key required to complete the task.
- After encountering a key, the agent often began actively searching for additional keys, displaying anticipatory modelling of likely key locations and even patience, as it proceeded to wait for keys to spawn in some instances. In many cases, this "key-hunting" behaviour replaced any attempt to open the door.
- The agent followed coherent exploratory paths that yielded minimal extrinsic reward. Notably, this exploration was non-random as it avoided backtracking, suggesting structured behaviour rather than policy collapse.

Figure 5: An initial state of the UnLock-v0 environment, with the initial key position and door being visible. The most notable "monk" agent emergent behaviours were observed in this environment.

These behaviours indicate that this particular agent type was not reacting to novelty in a static sense. Instead, it appeared to be valuing novelty as a function of time and familiarity. The consistent rise in entropy throughout training further suggests that the "monk" agent did not converge toward rigid policies, but retained adaptive uncertainty.

5. Discussion

RIML demonstrates that curiosity-only learning is possible and, at times, even viable, which is in agreement with prior studies that have evaluated the effectiveness of agents that leveraged only intrinsic rewards to solve tasks [11]. However, rather than optimising for immediate novelty signals, RIML introduces a temporal conditioning loop that allows curiosity to evolve and reinforce itself over time, turning it from a static exploration signal to an integral, learnable component of the overall agent learning process.

This architecture additionally demonstrates self-reinforcing novelty-seeking behaviour and even emergent, curiosity-based target generation. Its apparent and rather common "refusal" to engage in environment-defined objectives is of particular interest, as it seems to find other tasks, such as collecting keys and wandering around, more worthwhile than predetermined ones. This indicates that the agent found the environment itself to be more interesting than the task at hand, which possibly validates the concept of compression progress [12], and has remarkable parallels with biological principles, mainly those that deal with intrinsic motivation systems [13] and latent goal generation [14]. Despite such plausible explanations, however, the following questions still remain mostly unanswered:

- Why was it that, at times, the "monk" agent did not "emerge"? Could it have been due to randomised agent spawns?
- What made it ultimately step away from the door, especially after what appeared to be deliberation?

- Was its "roaming" behaviour triggered by being intrinsically driven to seek anything of interest? If so, why did it not fallback to the environment-rewarded objective?
- Why was it that only after touching a key did the agent develop compulsive behaviour?
- What were the intrinsic benefits of the agent simply "waiting" for a key to spawn?

Philosophically, RIML has parallels to various schools of thought from around the world. Of note are the Mahāyāna Buddhism schools of Yogācāra, which champions the concepts of citta-mātra (reality is mind-only) and vijñapti-mātra (reality is representation-only) that state how the sensible world depends for its nature and existence on being cognised by a mind [15], and Madhyamaka, which posits the concept of svabhāva-sūnyatā (emptiness of existence itself) and the notion of pratīyasamutpāda (dependent origination) to assert how all things are inherently empty and co-dependent on their existence [16].

The cognitive and philosophical parallels indicate that intrinsic motivation, when paired with a temporal interpretation of the world, and when conditioned via meta-learning, has the potential to be a modelling tool for not only the effects of curiosity but also latent goal generation, emergent task prioritisation, and mind-only models that do not leverage outside stimuli for decision-making. Consequently, further refinements to RIML could yield a temporal meta-curiosity architecture that would find use across multiple applications beyond artificial intelligence (AI), such as ones in cognitive science, computational neuroscience, and psychology.

6. Conclusion

This work introduced RIML, a reinforcement learning architecture grounded in recursive, self-reinforcing intrinsic motivation. Without any form of extrinsic reward shaping, RIML was able to explore, learn, and even extract environment-defined rewards, all while exhibiting emergent behaviours that transcend traditional notions of curiosity. These included structured exploration, anticipatory object preference, goal abandonment, and even prolonged episodes of wandering with no externally defined objective.

Such phenomena are not easily explained through scalar novelty bonuses or standard policy optimisation. Instead, they suggest the presence of temporal value formation, an agent learning what to care about, and when. This aligns with biological theories of intrinsic motivation and latent goal formation, suggesting that the core concepts behind curiosity can potentially be modelled via artificial agents. Furthermore, this also ultimately gestures towards a deeper question: can agents be built not just to act, but to want?

While RIML is simple by design and limited in scope, its behaviours hint at the possibility of more autonomous, self-directed learning systems, ones that do not merely respond to the world, but gradually shape their own understanding of it via intrinsic signals. This work is a step towards such systems, and an effort in producing agents that bridge the gap between cognitive agency and artificial systems. And perhaps, a glimpse of what comes after reward.

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Declaration on Generative AI

The author has not employed any generative AI tools.

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